

Antibacterial Efficacy Of Emodin From Polygonum Cuspidatum Against Oral Pathogens - In-Vitro Study

Research Article

Sarika Balaganesh¹, Jayashri Prabakar^{2*}, Meignana Arumugham Indiran³

¹ Post Graduate, Department Public Health Dentistry, Saveetha Dental College, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences, Saveetha University, No.162, Poonamallee High Road, Chennai 600077, Tamil Nadu, India.

² Senior Lecturer, Department of Public Health Dentistry, Saveetha Dental College, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences, Saveetha University, No.162, Poonamallee High Road, Chennai 600077, Tamil Nadu, India.

³ Professor and Head, Department of Public Health Dentistry, Saveetha Dental College, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences, Saveetha University, No.162, Poonamallee High Road, Chennai 600077, Tamil Nadu, India.

Abstract

Introduction: Oral diseases are among the major public health problems with dental caries and endodontic infection are the commonest affecting the mankind. The natural phytochemicals isolated from plants used as traditional medicines are considered as good alternatives than commercially available chemicals which have undesirable side effects. Emodin, an anthroquinone extracted from the roots of Polygonum cuspidatum was already proven to have antiviral, antibacterial and antifungal effects. Hence this present invitro study was conducted with the aim of determining the antibacterial efficacy of emodin against oral pathogens.

Materials and Methods: Then 25 mg Emodin was taken in a falcon tube and dissolved in 10 ml of Dimethylsulfoxide. The tube filled with this mixture was subjected to an agitator vortex mixer to mix emodin and dimethylsulfoxide effectively. After which the pipette was loaded with 25 microlitre, 50 microlitre, 100 microlitre, 200 microlitre. The prepared emodin extract was immersed in the

diffusion well of organisms Streptococcus mutans, Staphylococcus aureus, Lactobacillus acidophilus, Enterococcus faecalis, Candida albicans and zone of inhibition was measured.

Results: The zone of inhibition was measured for all the micro organisms loaded with different concentrations of emodin. Staphylococcus aureus showed activity in 100 microlitre and 200 microlitre concentrations than the other organisms. Secondary to Staphylococcus aureus, S.mutans also showed good activity with emodin in 100 and 200 microlitre concentrations. The effect of the anthroquinone emodin, was also present in rest of the organisms C.albicans, E.faecalis, L.acidophilus.

Conclusion: The study concludes that emodin had a better antibacterial efficacy against oral pathogens and hence proves that emodin can be used as a novel therapeutic agent for the prevention and control of oral diseases.

Keywords: Emodin; Polygonum cuspidatum; Anthraquinone; Phytochemicals.

Introduction

Oral diseases are among the most prevalent diseases globally and have serious health and economic burdens, greatly reduced quality of life for those affected [1]. The most prevalent and consequential oral diseases globally are dental caries, endodontic infections, periodontal disease, tooth loss, cancers of lips and oral cavity [2-4]. Dental caries is a biofilm-mediated, diet modulated, multifactorial, non-communicable, dynamic disease resulting in net

mineral loss of dental hard tissues [5]. Dental biofilm is the most common cause for dental caries. Dental biofilm is a consortium of microorganisms that stick to a tooth surface [6]. The microorganisms are embedded in an extracellular polymeric matrix. Streptococcus mutans is considered as a crucial pathogen in the development of dental caries. The major factors responsible for the cariogenicity of this pathogen include its ability to produce glycosyltransferases, synthesize insoluble glucans, survive at low pH thus maintaining the oral environment acidic and prone to demineralisation of teeth [7, 8]. Staphylococcus aureus survives

*Corresponding Author:

Jayashri Prabakar,
Senior Lecturer, Department of Public Health Dentistry, Saveetha Dental College, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences, Saveetha University, No.162, Poonamallee High Road, Chennai 600077, Tamil Nadu, India.
E-mail: jayashri.sdc@saveetha.com

Received: April 16, 2021

Accepted: September 20, 2021

Published: September 21, 2021

Citation: Sarika Balaganesh, Jayashri Prabakar, Meignana Arumugham Indiran. Antibacterial Efficacy Of Emodin From Polygonum Cuspidatum Against Oral Pathogens - In-Vitro Study. *Int J Dentistry Oral Sci.* 2021;8(9):4414-4417. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.19070/2377-8075-21000899>

Copyright: Jayashri Prabakar©2021. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

in a metabolically inactive state under harsh conditions and also contributes to the biofilm formation. *S.aureus* resist host defences or antibiotics [9]. *Enterococcus faecalis* is commonly detected in asymptomatic and persistent endodontic infections [10]. *Candida albicans* prevalence is significantly higher in children with early childhood caries and also has a major role in endodontic treatment failure [11]. *Lactobacilli* appears to be a planktonic, opportunistic settler that can gather and multiply in the oral cavity and cause dental caries.[12]

Despite advances in the development of invasive treatment these therapeutic strategies are often unable to control the progression of Dental caries. It has been reported that the use of natural products is one of the most successful strategies for the discovery of new techniques to prevent dental caries [13]. Herbal extracts are used for the treatment of various dental disorders [14, 15]. They are the effective alternative to antibiotics and represent a promising approach to prevention and therapeutic strategies for various oral infections. Herbal medicines have less side-effect in comparison with traditional medicines [16]. *Polygonum cuspidatum* is a herb widely distributed in China, Japan, Korea and North America and also reported to have enormous medicinal benefits [17]. Recent studies demonstrated that the herb also had antiviral, antibacterial and antifungal effects [18, 19].

The extracted components from *Polygonum cuspidatum* herb showed good antibacterial property. Emodin (1,3,8-trihydroxy-6-methylanthraquinone) is a major active component commonly present in *Polygonum cuspidatum*. It has been reported that emodin exhibits a wide range of biological activities including antibacterial, anticancer, anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetic and antioxidative activities [21]. Thus this study was conducted to make a further exploration of antibacterial compound Emodin from *P.cuspidatum* against oral pathogens as these pathogens are the essential contributors for poor oral health related quality of life.

Materials and Methods

Study setting

In vitro study.

Ethical approval

Saveetha Institute of review board.

Preparation of Emodin extract

Emodin is an anthraquinone derivative extracted from the herbs of *polygonum cuspidatum*. Emodin was purchased from a pharmaceutical company (Fig 1). Then 25 mg of this anthraquinone was taken in a falcon tube and dissolved in 10 ml of Dimethylsulfoxide. (Fig 2) The tube filled with this mixture was subjected to an agitator vortex mixer to mix emodin and dimethylsulfoxide effectively. After which the pipette was loaded with 25 microlitre, 50 microlitre, 100 microlitre, 200 microlitre.

Microbial analysis

Streptococcus mutans, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Candida albicans* were cultured and the loaded pipette with emodin mixture was placed in each culture plate of the microorganisms. The culture plates were kept for 24 hours and checked for the activity of the microorganisms (Fig 3). After 24 hours the zone of inhibition for all the organisms were measured.

Results

In this study, the antibacterial effect of emodin on *S.mutans*, *S.aureus*, *E.faecalis*, *C.albicans*, *Lactobacillus* were investigated. As shown in the Fig 3, growth of all pathogens was significantly reduced in the presence of emodin. This effect was revealed to be concentration dependent.

To determine the inhibitory effect of emodin on production of acid for all pathogens, the organisms were treated with different concentrations of emodin. The zone of inhibition was measured for all organisms using vernier caliper by determining the diameter of the inhibited site. The different concentrations used were the 25 microlitre, 50 microlitre, 100 microlitre, 200microlitre and there was a significant zone of inhibition.[Fig 3]. The measured

Figure 1. Emodin - powder form.

Figure 2. Preparation of Emodin extract.

zone of inhibition was tabulated [Table 1] and graphically represented [Fig 4].

This study proved that emodin was effective against all the oral pathogens. Streptococcus mutans and Staphylococcus aureus are the predominant organisms causing dental caries. Hence emodin can be used to prevent the formation of dental caries. Future studies can be done to detect the remineralization potential of emodin so that it can be used with dentifrices to promote better oral status.

Discussion

Considering the high incidence rate of dental caries and its detrimental effects in oral cavity, the development of novel strategies for its prevention and control are required [22]. Previous studies have demonstrated that natural products are promising candidates for novel anti cariogenic substances [23]. The present study revealed that emodin, a natural product, interfered with key

cariogenic factors of *S.mutans* and *S.aureus*. Emodin (1,3,8 –trihydroxy-6-methylanthraquinone) has demonstrated a broad range of antibacterial effect [24]. The present study revealed that emodin had excellent activity against the oral pathogens in vitro.

Emodin, a component derived from the roots and rhizomes of a number of plants including *Polygonum cuspidatum* and *Rheum undulatum* [25]. *Polygonum cuspidatum* had wide range of antibacterial activities. The components of *Polygonum cuspidatum* are the polydatin, reverastrol, anthraglycoside B and emodin [26]. All these components were proved to inhibit the glycolytic acid production and Gtf activity of *S.mutans* and *Streptococcus sobrinus* [27]. The dichloromethane fraction from *R.undulatum*, composed mainly of aloemodin, emodin, chrysophanol and physcion, has revealed inhibitory effects on the production of glycolytic acid by *S.mutans* on biofilms [28]. The other study done to test the anticariogenic property of emodin of *Streptococcus mutans* and the development of caries in rats revealed that the topical application of emodin reduced the incidence and sever-

Figure 3a. Streptococcus mutans with emodin extract.

Figure 3b. Enterococcus faecalis with emodin extract.

Figure 3c. Staphylococcus aureus with emodin extract.

Figure 3d. Candida albicans with emodin extract.

Figure 3e. L.acidophilus with emodin extract.

Table 1. Antimicrobial activity (Zone of inhibition) of the micro organisms.

Organisms	25 microlitre	50 microlitre	100 microlitre	200 microlitre
S.mutans	14mm	16mm	19mm	21mm
S.aureus	16mm	20mm	23mm	25mm
C.albicans	9mm	9mm	16mm	21mm
E.faecalis	9mm	10mm	16mm	17mm
Lactobacillus	9mm	9mm	14mm	15mm

Figure 4. Zone of inhibition against oral pathogens.

ity of carious lesions in the rats without affecting the percentage of *S.mutans* in the biofilms [29]. Previous study also suggests that emodin markedly suppressed the production of acid and the synthesis of insoluble glucan by *S.mutans* ATCC25175. The most important pathogenic property of *S.mutans* is the synthesis of insoluble glucans. Insoluble glucans promote the adhesive interaction of bacteria with tooth surface and contribute to formation of dental biofilm [30]. Accordingly this study was done to examine the antibacterial property of emodin against *S.mutans* and the rest of oral pathogens.

In the current study, emodin had antibacterial efficacy against the oral pathogens tested in this study. These results suggest that emodin may be responsible for the antibacterial activity of microorganisms tested. Since the literature says that matrix metalloproteinases, are involved in the pathogenesis of dental caries [31]. Emodin has demonstrated to have inhibitory potential against matrix metalloproteinases invitro and invivo [32]. So the results obtained in this study may also suggests that emodin may have the antibacterial efficacy as they inhibit the activity of matrix metalloproteinases. Future studies may be needed to support this point on emodin is active against the matrix metalloproteinases.

Summarizing the study, Emodin significantly attenuated the growth of the oral pathogens in vitro. Hence this result suggests that emodin may be used as a novel therapeutic agent for the oral infections threatening the mankind.

Conclusion

The results of the present study proved that emodin which is the component of *Polygonum cuspidatum* had better antibacterial efficacy against the oral microflora which gives an insight as this component can be used as an anticariogenic agent.

References

- [1]. Jin LJ, Lamster IB, Greenspan JS, Pitts NB, Scully C, Warnakulasuriya S. Global burden of oral diseases: emerging concepts, management and interplay with systemic health. *Oral Dis.* 2016 Oct;22(7):609-19. Pubmed PMID: 26704694.
- [2]. Rôças IN, Siqueira JF Jr, Santos KR. Association of *Enterococcus faecalis* with different forms of periradicular diseases. *J Endod.* 2004 May;30(5):315-20. Pubmed PMID: 15107642.
- [3]. Pereira CA, Romeiro RL, Costa AC, Machado AK, Junqueira JC, Jorge AO. Susceptibility of *Candida albicans*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Streptococcus mutans* biofilms to photodynamic inactivation: an in vitro study. *Lasers Med Sci.* 2011 May;26(3):341-8. Pubmed PMID: 21069408.
- [4]. Smiech-Slomkowska G, Jablonska-Zrobek J. The effect of oral health education on dental plaque development and the level of caries-related *Streptococcus mutans* and *Lactobacillus* spp. *Eur J Orthod.* 2007 Apr;29(2):157-60. Pubmed PMID: 17488998.
- [5]. Pitts NB, Zero DT, Marsh PD, Ekstrand K, Weintraub JA, Ramos-Gomez F, et al. Dental caries. *Nature reviews Disease primers.* 2017 May 25;3(1):1-6.
- [6]. Larsen T, Fiehn NE. Dental biofilm infections - an update. *APMIS.* 2017 Apr;125(4):376-384. Pubmed PMID: 28407420.
- [7]. Krzyściak W, Jurczak A, Kościelniak D, Bystrowska B, Skalniak A. The virulence of *Streptococcus mutans* and the ability to form biofilms. *Eur J Clin Microbiol Infect Dis.* 2014 Apr;33(4):499-515. Pubmed PMID: 24154653.
- [8]. Lemos JA, Palmer SR, Zeng L, Wen ZT, Kajfasz JK, Freires IA, et al. The biology of *Streptococcus mutans*. *Gram-Positive Pathogens.* 2019 Oct 1:435-48.
- [9]. Schilcher K, Horswill AR. *Staphylococcal Biofilm Development: Structure, Regulation, and Treatment Strategies.* *Microbiol Mol Biol Rev.* 2020 Aug 12;84(3):e00026-19. Pubmed PMID: 32792334.

- [10]. Tennert C, Fuhrmann M, Wittmer A, Karygianni L, Altenburger MJ, Pelz K, et al. New bacterial composition in primary and persistent/secondary endodontic infections with respect to clinical and radiographic findings. *J Endod.* 2014 May;40(5):670-7. Pubmed PMID: 24767562.
- [11]. Mergoni G, Percudani D, Lodi G, Bertani P, Manfredi M. Prevalence of *Candida* Species in Endodontic Infections: Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *J Endod.* 2018 Nov;44(11):1616-1625.e9. Pubmed PMID: 30241680.
- [12]. Caufield PW, Schön CN, Saraithong P, Li Y, Argimón S. Oral Lactobacilli and Dental Caries: A Model for Niche Adaptation in Humans. *J Dent Res.* 2015 Sep;94(9 Suppl):110S-8S. Pubmed PMID: 25758458.
- [13]. Jeon JG, Rosalen PL, Falsetta ML, Koo H. Natural products in caries research: current (limited) knowledge, challenges and future perspective. *Caries Res.* 2011;45(3):243-63. Pubmed PMID: 21576957.
- [14]. Şener B, Kiliç M. Herbal extracts used in dental disorders.
- [15]. Buggapati L. Herbs in dentistry. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Science Invention.* 2016 Oct;5(6):07-12.
- [16]. Verma S, Singh SP. Current and future status of herbal medicines. *Veterinary world.* 2008 Nov 1;1(11):347.
- [17]. Peng W, Qin R, Li X, Zhou H. Botany, phytochemistry, pharmacology, and potential application of *Polygonum cuspidatum* Sieb. et Zucc.: a review. *J Ethnopharmacol.* 2013 Jul 30;148(3):729-45. Pubmed PMID: 23707210.
- [18]. Li L, Song X, Yin Z, Jia R, Li Z, Zhou X, et al. The antibacterial activity and action mechanism of emodin from *Polygonum cuspidatum* against *Haemophilus parvus* in vitro. *Microbiol Res.* 2016 May-Jun;186-187:139-45. Pubmed PMID: 27242151. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27242151/>
- [19]. Zhang H, Li C, Kwok ST, Zhang QW, Chan SW. A Review of the Pharmacological Effects of the Dried Root of *Polygonum cuspidatum* (Hu Zhang) and Its Constituents. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med.* 2013;2013:208349. Pubmed PMID: 24194779.
- [20]. Wu X, Li Q, Feng Y, Ji Q. Antitumor Research of the Active Ingredients from Traditional Chinese Medical Plant *Polygonum Cuspidatum*. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med.* 2018 Nov 21;2018:2313021. Pubmed PMID: 30584449.
- [21]. Wang L, Qiu P, Long XF, Zhang S, Zeng ZG, Tian YQ. Comparative analysis of chemical constituents, antimicrobial and antioxidant activities of ethylacetate extracts of *Polygonum cuspidatum* and its endophytic actinomycete, *Streptomyces* sp. A0916. *Chin J Nat Med.* 2016 Feb;14(2):117-123. Pubmed PMID: 26968677.
- [22]. Ogoina D, Onyemelukwe GC. The role of infections in the emergence of non-communicable diseases (NCDs): Compelling needs for novel strategies in the developing world. *J Infect Public Health.* 2009;2(1):14-29. Pubmed PMID: 20701857.
- [23]. Song X, Xia YX, He ZD, Zhang HJ. A review of natural products with anti-biofilm activity. *Current Organic Chemistry.* 2018 Apr 1;22(8):789-817.
- [24]. Yan X, Gu S, Shi Y, Cui X, Wen S, Ge J. The effect of emodin on *Staphylococcus aureus* strains in planktonic form and biofilm formation in vitro. *Arch Microbiol.* 2017 Nov;199(9):1267-1275. Pubmed PMID: 28616631.
- [25]. Rokaya MB, Maršik P, Münzbergová Z. Active constituents in *Polygonum acuminatum* and *Rheum australe* (Polygonaceae) roots: A variation between cultivated and naturally growing plants. *Biochemical Systematics and Ecology.* 2012 Apr 1;41:83-90.
- [26]. Zhang D, Li X, Hao D, Li G, Xu B, Ma G, et al. Systematic purification of polydatin, resveratrol and anthraglycoside B from *Polygonum cuspidatum* Sieb. et Zucc. Separation and purification technology. 2009 Apr 20;66(2):329-39.
- [27]. Ban SH, Kwon YR, Pandit S, Lee YS, Yi HK, Jeon JG. Effects of a bio-assay guided fraction from *Polygonum cuspidatum* root on the viability, acid production and glucosyltransferase of *mutans streptococci*. *Fitoterapia.* 2010 Jan;81(1):30-4. Pubmed PMID: 19616082.
- [28]. Cheng L, Li J, He L, Zhou X. Natural products and caries prevention. *Caries Res.* 2015;49 Suppl 1:38-45. Pubmed PMID: 25871417.
- [29]. Xu JS, Cui Y, Liao XM, Tan XB, Cao X. Effect of emodin on the cariogenic properties of *Streptococcus mutans* and the development of caries in rats. *Exp Ther Med.* 2014 Oct;8(4):1308-1312. Pubmed PMID: 25187845.
- [30]. Horz P, Guggenheim B, Schmid R. Carbohydrates in pooled dental plaque. *Caries Res.* 1972;6(2):103-21. Pubmed PMID: 4502278.
- [31]. Jain A, Bahuguna R. Role of matrix metalloproteinases in dental caries, pulp and periapical inflammation: An overview. *J Oral Biol Craniofac Res.* 2015 Sep-Dec;5(3):212-8. Pubmed PMID: 26605147.
- [32]. Lu HF, Lai KC, Hsu SC, Lin HJ, Kuo CL, Liao CL, et al. Involvement of matrix metalloproteinases on the inhibition of cells invasion and migration by emodin in human neuroblastoma SH-SY5Y cells. *Neurochem Res.* 2009 Sep;34(9):1575-83. Pubmed PMID: 19291397.